

was obtained from an in vitro culture with a high growth rate (trial 1). FW doubling was reduced to 3.06 times and DW 3.25 times when the inoculum was obtained from storage cultures with a minimal growth rate (trial 2). FW doubling fell to 3.14 times and DW to 2.94 times when the inoculum came from storage cultures with near-stationary growth rate, that had been subjected to very low (less than 10 klux) light intensities (trial 3).

Regardless of preinoculation conditions, the growth rate of this isolate (FW measurement) showed an initial lag phase followed by an increase during the first 7 days of the trial. During FW growth rate increase, growth rate determined by DW was decreased correspondingly. At 7 days, the DW and FW growth rates were similar (Table 2).

Another azolla isolate, Amazon-R, was

Table 2. Daily growth rates of Monteria-3.

Time lapse	Daily growth rate					
	Trial 1 ^a		Trial 2 ^b		Trial 3 ^c	
	FW	DW	FW	DW	FW	DW
1-day	0.24 ± 0.06	0.54	0	0.39 ± 0.14	0	0.47 ± 0.24
2-day	0.53 ± 0.01	0.69 ± 0.08	0.07 ± 0.06	0.26 ± 0.13	0.21 ± 0.07	0.43 ± 0.10
3-day	0.43 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.04	0.37 ± 0.07	0.55 ± 0.10	0.40 ± 0.05	0.52 ± 0.03
4-day	—	—	—	—	0.38 ± 0.06	0.51 ± 0.04
5-day	—	—	—	—	0.43 ± 0.08	0.46 ± 0.07
6-day	—	—	—	—	0.46 ± 0.02	0.47 ± 0.03
7-day	0.46 ± 0.02	0.48 ± 0.02	0.44 ± 0.03	0.47 ± 0.02	0.44 ± 0.05	0.44 ± 0.02
14day	0.30 ± 0.02	0.24 ± 0.02	—	—	0.33 ± 0.02	0.29 ± 0.02

^aTrial 1: no difference between storage and growth trial conditions. ^bTrial 2: inoculum not in active growth phase. ^cTrial 3: inoculum not in active growth and stored under < 10 klux.

incubated for 24 hours under stress parameters (darkness, 35°C). Subsequent FW diurnal growth rate remained consistently depressed (0.33) for 2 weeks. DW rate decreased 0.56 to 0.38 in 1 week, and to 0.27 in 2 weeks. Nonstressed replications showed a stable FW rate (0.54 to 0.53) and a higher, albeit decreasing, DW rate

(0.63-0.49) in the first week. At 2 weeks FW (0.31) and the DW (0.31) growth rates resembled those of the stressed replications. Total doublings were 2.24 FW and 2.67 DW after 7 days for stressed samples, and 3.73 FW and 3.43 DW for nonstressed ones. □

Differential tolerance of rices for low-sulfur soils

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Forty-three lines or varieties were studied for reaction to low-sulfur soils in irrigated fields during the wet season in South Sulawesi. Soil at the test site was a Typic Tropaquept with H 6 2, 2.66% organic matter, 4.2 µg SO₄²⁻-S/kg, 23 mmol cation exchange capacity/kg, and clay loam texture.

Entries were grown in unreplicated treated and untreated plots. Eighty kg S/ha as ammonium sulfate was applied to the treated plot, and 100 N, 26 P, and 50 K kg/ha were applied to both plots. Each entry was planted in four 3-m-long rows at 20 × 20 cm spacing.

Plant height, tiller number, days to maturity, and grain yield per hill varied by variety. Marked differences were observed in grain yield per hill and days to maturity. Using those parameters, the 43 entries were divided into 4 groups: similar grain yield and days to maturity for both treatments, different grain yield and similar days to maturity, similar grain yield

Reaction of some rice lines or varieties to low-sulfur soil by grain yield and days to maturity.

Line or variety	Grain yield (g/hill)		Days to maturity	
	+S	-S	+S	-S
Similar yield, maturity				
IR34	74.2	67.9	131	135
IR2070-24-1-5-1	56.2	49.6	131	135
Pulu bolong	36.1	33.8	147	149
Ase lelling	50.4	50.9	149	149
Mean of 9 lines or varieties	52.9	51.8	136	138
Similar yield, different maturity				
IR20	75.7	71.1	119	133
IR.2307-233-3	62.1	61.1	117	135
SPR6726-76-2-3	50.8	51.1	115	126
Pelita I/1	76.7	70.7	128	135
Mean of 9 lines or varieties	61.0	61.8	121	134
Different yield, similar maturity				
IR28	60.8	34.5	112	115
IR30	73.7	40.6	112	115
IR36	63.6	51.8	112	115
Banda	79.8	33.4	159	161
Mean of 12 lines or varieties	59.5	38.3	131	133
Different yield, maturity				
1132153-26-3-5-4	64.2	48.9	115	131
B2376-9-1	80.9	61.3	115	128
B462c-Pn-1-3	66.0	41.5	117	126
Syntha	78.0	59.3	128	140
Mean of 13 lines or varieties	62.9	42.6	118	132

and different days to maturity, and different grain yield and days to maturity (see table). Treated and Untreated plots were considered different when they

varied by at least 15% in yield and 7 days in maturity. Results suggest that rices have different reactions to low-S soil in terms of the plant parameters measured.